

Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO): The Case of TEVET Institutions in Zambia

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
31 August 2024

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ABSTRACT

This review article examines the impact of Entrepreneurship Education programs (EEP) on Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) within Technical Education Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training (TEVET) institutions in Zambia. By synthesizing findings from existing literature, the article provides a comprehensive understanding of how EEP influences entrepreneurial behaviors among vocational students. Key dimensions of IEO affected by EEP, including innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, autonomy, and competitive aggressiveness, are explored. The review discusses various pedagogical approaches used in EEP, highlights the challenges faced in delivering effective EEP, and identifies opportunities for improvement. The article concludes with recommendations for policymakers and educators to enhance the effectiveness of EEP in fostering entrepreneurial mindsets, thereby contributing to Zambia's economic development goals.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO), Entrepreneurship Education Program (EEP), TEVET, Zambia

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is vital in economic development, job creation (Mwange, 2018) and innovation (Libingi, 2024; Nor, 2024; Likando et al., 2023). Entrepreneurial activities have made a significant contribution to the overall economic growth and resilience of a country by promoting competition among entrants as well as fostering new startups. Entrepreneurship has been identified as an important tool for addressing high levels of unemployment and poverty in most developing countries including Zambia (Libingi and Bbenkele, 2024). In this regard, Zambia has integrated entrepreneurship education (EE) into its technical education vocational entrepreneurship training (TEVET) curriculum to enhance students' entrepreneurial skills that would enable them create jobs instead of seeking employment.

Policymakers and educators have acknowledged the importance of entrepreneurship in national development. The belief is that nurturing an entrepreneurial culture within academic institutions can provide novel solutions to social and economic challenges. This is especially true given that millions of Zambians rely on traditional sectors like agriculture, mining and services for their livelihoods. Using entrepreneurship as a mechanism through which to diversify the base of the economy would reduce reliance on these

traditional domains with impacts being seen in terms of sustainable growth.

Entrepreneurship Education Programs (EEP), therefore, aims at preparing individuals to identify business opportunities while providing them with knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for exploiting these opportunities (Ogunode and Leah, 2024). EE programmes mainly consist of both theoretical courses such as business planning, leadership (Masase-Muza et al, 2022) marketing research, financial management processes, innovation processes etc., or practical programs aimed at nurturing creativity; risk taking; proactive nature among many other student behaviors that encourage entrepreneurship. The aim is to embed EE into TEVET curriculum to make both trainers and learners who are ready to pursue innovation-driven economies.

Integrating EEP into Zambia's TEVET institutions falls within the country's broader Vision 2030 which seeks to transform Zambia into a middle-income prosperous nation by 2030. The vision focuses on building a skilled workforce capable of contributing towards economic growth while reducing unemployment rates in the country. Technical Education Vocational Entrepreneurship Training Authority (TEVETA) of Zambia government has made tremendous efforts to integrate EE into vocational and technical training

programs. These initiatives intend to create labor force that will respond to the needs of the labor market through self-employment.

However, despite the well-established benefits of EEP, there are several challenges associated with its implementation. First, there is a gap between what students learn theoretically in class and what they apply practically in their economic activities as entrepreneurs. Additionally, resources that must be dedicated towards this purpose are inexistent as well as trained facilitators to run EE programmes efficiently (Galvao et al., 2020). In this respect, continuous evaluation and improvement of EE programs appear necessary so that they can effectively encourage entrepreneurial behaviors among trainees.

This review paper explores how entrepreneurship education Programs (EEP) affects individual entrepreneurial orientation (IEO) of students, within the context of TEVET institutions in Zambia. The article aims at providing an integrated knowledge on various dimensions such as innovativeness; risk taking; proactiveness; autonomy; competitive aggressiveness by synthesizing information from extant literature regarding how EEP influences IEO. It also outlines different pedagogical approaches used while teaching entrepreneurship education, their effectiveness and highlights challenges and opportunities available in enhancing these programs. Finally, recommendations for policy makers and educators are provided to improve the efficiency of EEP towards developing entrepreneurship mindsets thereby supporting Zambia's economic development objectives.

The objectives of this review article are:

1. To synthesize existing literature on the impact of EEP on IEO in TEVET institutions.
2. To identify the key dimensions of IEO influenced by EEP in TEVET institutions of Zambia.
3. To examine the pedagogical approaches used in EEP and their effectiveness.
4. To highlight challenges and opportunities in delivering EEP in TEVET institutions in Zambia.
5. To provide recommendations for improving EEPs to foster entrepreneurial orientation.

This article presents the current level of EEPs within Zambia's TEVET institutions through systematic review of the literature and suggest some ways its impact can be intensified as a result thereof; hence contributing to efforts aimed at developing a skilled, entrepreneurial workforce capable of driving economic transformation in Zambia

METHODOLOGY

This review article employs a systematic literature review methodology to synthesize findings from existing studies on EE and IEO in TEVET institutions. The methodology involves the following steps:

1. Literature Search:

Databases: Google Scholar, JSTOR, Science Direct, and institutional repositories.

Keywords: "Entrepreneurship Education Programs," "Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation," "TEVET," "Zambia," "vocational training," and "entrepreneurial mindset."

Inclusion Criteria: Peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and relevant thesis documents published within the last 20 years.

Exclusion Criteria: Studies not focused on TEVET institutions, articles in languages other than English, and non-peer-reviewed sources.

2. Screening and Selection:

Title and abstract screening to identify relevant studies.

Full-text review of selected articles to ensure they meet inclusion criteria.

3. Data Extraction:

Key information extracted includes study objectives, methodology, key findings, and conclusions.

Data categorized based on themes related to EEP and IEO, such as pedagogical approaches, challenges, and dimensions of IEO.

4. Synthesis and Analysis:

Thematic analysis to identify common findings and discrepancies across studies.

Critical evaluation of the quality and rigor of the studies reviewed.

Synthesis of findings to draw comprehensive conclusions about the influence of EEP on IEO in TEVET institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)

The entrepreneurial orientation (EO) is a critical concept in entrepreneurship that encompasses the organization's strategic practices, processes and decisions used to identify and exploit new opportunities. The EO concept has multiple dimensions which include innovativeness, risk taking, proactiveness, autonomy and competitive aggressiveness (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996).

Innovativeness refers to the inclination of a Company or individual to engage in and support fresh ideas, novelty, experimentation as well as creative processes that can result into new products services or technological processes (Hult et al., 2003). This crucial dimension drives the development of distinctive solutions and ability to remain ahead in competing markets, with strong leadership (Masase-Muza et al, 2022).

Risk-taking refers to making significant resource commitments towards opportunities where failure might be very costly. This dimension relates with uncertainty inherent in entrepreneurial activities and the audacity of taking steps into unknown territories despite potential losses (Miller, 1983). Firms and individuals who are highly risk inclined are more likely to be engaged in ventures that could bring about

very high returns.

Pro-activeness is like forward-looking perspective that anticipates future needs, changes, and trends within marketplace. An initiative taken by fore sightedness for taking upcoming opportunities even before they occur rather than reacting after event occurs is called pro-activeness (Lumpkin & Dess, 2001). Proactive entities are often the first movers gaining competitive advantage through early market entry and creating a strong market presence.

Autonomy involves independent action by an individual or team that presents an idea/vision till it gets effected (Lumpkin et al., 2009). For creativity ideas thrive without being hindered by organizational constraints autonomy is of great importance.

Competitive aggressiveness represents how intense a company tries to outdo its competitors. It entails combative posture together with strong offensive strategy aimed at achieving market leadership position (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). This dimension underscores the importance of competitive spirit and ambition to succeed in a crowded marketplace.

EO has usually been considered at the organizational level, where it has been identified with firm performance and strategic management practices (Covin & Slevin, 1989; Wiklund & Shepherd, 2003). Research has demonstrated that firms with strong EO are more likely to have higher levels of performance because they are capable of innovation, taking calculated risks and proactively addressing market needs (Rauch et al., 2009).

Nevertheless, recent research focuses on understanding EO at the individual level called Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO). IEO examines how these entrepreneurial behaviors manifest within individuals particularly in educational settings as well as personal development (Bolton & Lane, 2012). It is realized that entrepreneurial orientation is not only a firm-level attribute but also a personal trait that can influence career choices, personal initiatives and overall entrepreneurial success.

Studies on IEO emphasize the importance of educational interventions like Entrepreneurship Education (EE) aimed at cultivating these entrepreneurial traits among students and aspiring entrepreneurs, especially in Zambia (Likando et al., 2023). For example, Bolton and Lane (2012) developed a scale for measuring IEO and found out that educational programs could significantly enhance student's entrepreneurial orientation by promoting such characteristics as innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness.

One purpose of integrating EO into educational curricula is to train people who will be able to manage dynamics of entrepreneurship effectively. This will lead institutions into fostering a new class of entrepreneurs with the necessary mindsets and skills to enhance economic growth and innovation (Wang, Ellinger, & Wu, 2013).

Entrepreneurship Education (EEP)

Entrepreneurship Education Program (EEP) is about learning entrepreneurial skills which assist in creating new businesses, as well as promoting creativity, entrepreneurial intentions, orientation and innovation. This has been taught in schools across the globe including Zambia, so that students can think like entrepreneurs (Gorostiaga et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022) as it has been seen to promote innovativeness, proactiveness and risk-taking (Perez et al., 2024).

For instance, there are EE programs designed to create an environment which enables a person to take advantage of business opportunities by providing them with relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes and an improvement in all business dimensions including financial performance (Gedeon, 2017; Chiwele and Mwange, 2024). Such programs normally involve teaching of theoretical ideas mixed with practical experiences like preparing business plans, carrying out market research, managing finances as well as learning about innovative processes (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

Global Integration of EE

The global education system recognizes EE as a significant component within it. For example, the European Commission has stressed on the significance of EE through its “Entrepreneurship 2020 Action Plan” targeted at supporting and fostering entrepreneurship at all levels of education (European Commission, 2013). The plan proposes that from primary school to tertiary institutions entrepreneurship should be included in curriculums for children to be exposed from an early stage.

In America, several initiatives have been put in place towards assimilation of EE within the educational systems. Programs such as Junior Achievement and NFTE provide hands-on experience on entrepreneurship skills among students thereby making them more enlightened on conducting business (Bruyere, 2021).

EE in Africa

One way that African countries have tried addressing high unemployment rates and stimulating economic growth is by adopting EE. As an example, South Africa has mainstreamed EE into its national curriculum through subjects like Economic and Management Sciences at Primary School level as well as Business Studies at High School level (Isaacs et al., 2007). The aim of these activities is to instill entrepreneurial thinking in students so that they would be better placed for the labour market.

Furthermore, in Nigeria there have been established EE programs in tertiary institutions with a view to motivating students to take up entrepreneurship as a career. Additionally, Nigerian government has also instituted entrepreneurship development centers to provide training and support services for aspiring entrepreneurs (Ojeifo, 2012).

EE in Zambia

The initiative of incorporating EE into the education system of Zambia has been led by Technical Education Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training Authority (TEVETA). Under TEVETA, these programs are implemented in vocational and technical institutions so that they can equip learners with skills necessary for self-employment (TEVETA, 2020) and promote their leadership skills (Masase-Muza et al., 2022; Bwalya, 2022).

Zambia's ambition of becoming a prosperous middle-income country by 2030 is closely linked to the recognition of EE by government through curriculum inclusion. Through EE incorporation into its syllabus, Zambia hopes to develop an enterprise culture which may promote economic growth and reduce unemployment rate (GRZ, 2006).

Impact of EEP on Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) and Innovation

Studies indicate that exposure to entrepreneurial education significantly enhances entrepreneurial intentions (Kalitanyi and Bbenkele, 2018; Mwange, 2018) as well as innovative behaviors among students. For instance, Souitaris et al.'s study (2007) showed that involvement in entrepreneurship programs increased both the tendency towards starting businesses as well as entrepreneurial intentions amongst students. Similarly, Sánchez reported from his research work that EE increases student's self-efficacy and their entrepreneurial skills leading to increased levels of how much individuals engage themselves in entrepreneurial activities.

Nevertheless, not only does EE facilitate new business venturing but also innovation within existing organizations. Thus, by supporting creative thinking and problem-solving capabilities the program enables individuals' effective participation in innovative processes taking place within dynamic business environments (Rae & Carswell, 2001).

Though it has its upsides, implementing entrepreneurship education encounters a variety of bottlenecks. A key constraint is untrained teachers who lack both theoretical knowledge on entrepreneurship and practical experience in the field. This can impede the delivery of EE programs effectively (Nabi et al., 2018).

Another challenge arises from resistance to change within educational institutions. Conventional schooling systems may be slow in embracing new teaching methods as well as curricula that focus on experiential learning and entrepreneurship (Neck & Greene, 2011). In addition, there may be scarce resources and infrastructure to provide support for EE initiatives especially in developing countries (Nabi et al., 2018).

To overcome these challenges and enhance the effectiveness of EE, several recommendations can be made:

1. **Training Educators:** Providing professional development opportunities for educators to gain practical experience in entrepreneurship, business leadership and learn innovative teaching methods can improve the

delivery of EE programs (Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2006; Bwalya, 2022).

2. **Curriculum Development:** Developing a comprehensive EE curriculum that includes both theoretical and practical components can ensure that students receive a well-rounded education in entrepreneurship (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008).

3. **Experiential Learning:** Incorporating experiential learning opportunities such as internships, business simulations and entrepreneurship projects will help students to apply their knowledge into practice (Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

4. **Collaboration with Industry:** Building partnerships with businesses and industry professionals can provide students with real-world insights and mentorship, enhancing their entrepreneurial learning experiences (Hannon, 2005).

5. **Policy Support:** Governments should develop policies that support the integration of EE into educational systems while providing funding and resources to back up such initiatives (European Commission, 2013).

Entrepreneurship Education (EE) is important for cultivating entrepreneurial skills, creativity and innovation among learners who would be game changers in their communities (Likando et al., 2023; Mwange, 2018). It is being integrated in the educational systems of various countries such as Zambia to develop entrepreneurship mindsets geared towards economic growth and job creation. Despite the challenges, EE has numerous advantages and through the right backing and improvements, EE can significantly contribute to nurturing future entrepreneurs.

TEVET System in Zambia

With TEVETA as its regulator, the Technical Education Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training Authority (TEVET) offers vocational training courses while at the same time enhancing entrepreneurial abilities through EE. This is expected to enable it to create a workforce that is market driven and is more inclined into self-employment (Mukuni, 2020; Mwange, 2018). As per TEVETA's strategic initiatives, the quality and relevance of vocational trainings must be improved so that graduands are suitably endowed with industrial skills and prepared for business start-ups (TEVETA, 2020).

Curriculum Development and Implementation

Entrepreneurial education has been incorporated in various vocational programs through a comprehensive curriculum developed by TEVETA. Consequently, this curriculum is designed to produce students who have both technical knowledge as well as the ability to enterprise in different economic environments. This program teaches students how to develop business plans; it also touches on financial literacy, marketing among other practical experiences like internships and business simulations (TEVETA, 2020).

Partnerships and Collaboration

Several stakeholders are involved in collaboration with TEVETA including government institutions, private sector firms and international partners which enhances effectiveness of their programs. This calls for partnerships that will allow sharing of resources like mentoring opportunities thus ensuring that the skills provided by this training are up to date with what industry requires now. For instance, local businesses' partnership enables learners to practice what they have learnt theoretically through internships or apprenticeships thereby mopping out gap between theoretical knowledge obtained in classrooms from real world applications (World Bank, 2018).

Challenges and Opportunities

Though progress has been made on embedding entrepreneurship education within the TEVET system there remains quite a few challenges. One major challenge is lack of funding required to sufficiently support extensive trainings and mentorship programs needed for effective EE. Furthermore, educators need continuous professional development for them not be left behind with current trends in entrepreneurship and pedagogy (World Bank, 2018).

Despite these challenges, there are many opportunities to improve the impact of EE on the TEVET system. This can be done by investing more resources into vocational infrastructure; increasing private sector participation or use more technologically developed teaching methods to enhance both the quality and coverage of this kind of education. Moreover, creating a conducive policy environment that supports innovations and entrepreneurialism is essential for maintaining long term growth and impact of EE efforts (GRZ, 2006).

Impact on Students and the Economy

The integration of EE into the TEVET system has shown positive impacts on students and the broader economy (Libingi and Bbenkele, 2024). It is more likely that graduates from TEVET institutions who receive entrepreneurship training will venture into their own businesses thus contributing to employment creation as well as economic growth. Furthermore, such graduates tend to be more innovative and proactive which are needed drivers for economic development in Zambia (Mukuni, 2020).

Research shows that learners with entrepreneurship education record high levels of entrepreneurial intentions and self-efficacy. A study conducted by Zampetakis et al., (2009) found out that entrepreneurship education significantly boosts learners' confidence regarding being an entrepreneur thereby enhancing their likelihoods of entering this field later in life. This is aligned with Zambia's Vision 2030 which seeks to encourage an entrepreneurial culture as a means towards achieving sustainable economic growth (GRZ, 2006).

In Zambia, through integrating entrepreneurship education in the TEVET system which is very critical in developing a

skilled and entrepreneurial workforce. Therefore, with addressing the existing challenges as well as making use of available opportunities, the system can enhance its impact more contributing to the economic growth and development of the country. These benefits can be sustained and magnified by continuously investing in education, working collaboratively with industry partners as well as crafting supportive policies for entrepreneurship education within TEVET.

EE's Impact on IEO

According to some research, EE highly improves students' IEO levels largely in terms of innovation, competitive aggressiveness, achievement orientation, learning orientation, passion and proactiveness (Lumpkin & Dess 1996; Gorostiaga et al., 2019; Ogunode and Leah, 2024). However, these dimensions have little significance in risk-taking and autonomy hence there is need for betterment in EEP delivery as evidenced from the TEVET institutions in Zambia (Libingi and Bbenkele, 2024).

Innovation

EE has been found out to promote creativity and innovation among students. They become able to think outside their comfort zone through engagement in activities that require creative problem-solving or coming up with new ideas. This therefore indicates that design thinking programs; ideation sessions could be encouraged and project-based learning thereby helping students innovate or apply knowledge differently (Rae & Melton 2016).

Competitive Aggressiveness

Students who undergo EE tend to develop stronger competition mentality because they are often put under scenarios where they need to compete so that best business ideas or solutions may be developed. Such kind of competition drives them harder so that they can perform well all through their workplace endeavors. To survive in entrepreneurship this experience is important since it helps one attain competitive aggressiveness (Bacigalupo et al., 2016).

Achievement Orientation

Clear objectives setting and attaining them benefit from adopting EE approach. Through practical exercises including real-world challenges students learn about importance of goal setting as well as perseverance and resilience. Such kind of orientation to achievement is important in entrepreneurship since it makes people forge ahead with their business objectives despite obstacles (Morris et al., 2013).

Learning Orientation

EE encourages learning orientation among students. This encompasses continuous learning, curiosity and adaptability to changing environments. Entrepreneurship is a dynamic field and those who keep on learning as well as developing are better placed to exploit new opportunities (Kuratko 2014).

Passion

Successful entrepreneurship comes out of passion. Thus, EE that stirs and kindles the flame of passion for entrepreneurship can be impactful for a considerable time on the students' lives. Passionate people are likely to persist even when faced with problems so that their entrepreneurial goals are met (Cardon et al., 2009).

Proactiveness

Proactiveness entails taking initiative as well as identifying future challenges or opportunities. This proactive mindset is built by EE which enables learners to identify gaps in the market and respond according to emerging trends. Therefore, being proactive will make one to become a first mover thereby giving him/her competitive edge (Frese & Gielnik 2014).

Risk-Taking

While this generally strengthens entrepreneurial skills, the impact of EE on risk-taking remains unclear (Libingi and Bbenkele, 2024), with more propensity to take risk being high in males compared to female (Astuti et al., 2024). There could be lack of enough exposure of many EE programmes to risk scenarios or insufficient support in terms of developing risk management abilities among scholars involved herein. Then we need some curriculum readjustment for students' better preparedness towards inherent risks associated with being entrepreneurs (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006).

Autonomy

Similarly, autonomy dimension is not highly improved through EE programs. Autonomy means self-direction and independence in decision-making processes thus helping an individual know his/her way forward without any influence from other people around him/her at times. To instill autonomy, these programmes should insist much on self-sufficiency besides encouraging student led projects only possible through independent leadership opportunities provided at school levels. This helps in developing self-confident individuals with critical thinking skills necessary for entrepreneurship (Lumpkin et al., 2009).

EE has several positive impacts, but it is not effective enough to enhance all dimensions of IEO fully because some challenges do exist. Some of these challenges are as follows:

Limited Practical Experience: Many EE programs focus heavily on theoretical knowledge, with insufficient opportunities for hands-on experience. Practical exposure through internships, simulations, and real-life projects is crucial for developing entrepreneurial skills (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012).

Inadequate Mentorship: Effective EE requires mentorship from experienced entrepreneurs who can provide guidance and support. However, many programs lack access to mentors who can share practical insights and help students navigate the entrepreneurial landscape (St-Jean & Audet, 2012).

Resource Constraints: Financial and infrastructural limitations can impede the delivery of high-quality EE. Schools may lack the necessary resources to implement comprehensive EE programs, such as access to technology, funding for projects, and collaboration opportunities with industry (Nabi et al., 2018).

Educator Training: Educators themselves may lack the entrepreneurial experience and training needed to effectively teach EE. Continuous professional development and exposure to entrepreneurial practices are essential for educators to effectively mentor and inspire students (Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2006).

To address these challenges and enhance the effectiveness of EE in fostering IEO, the following recommendations are proposed:

Enhance Practical Learning: Incorporate more practical elements into EE programs, such as business simulations, internships, and project-based learning. This approach provides students with real-world experience and a deeper understanding of entrepreneurial processes (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012).

Strengthen Mentorship: Establish mentorship programs that connect students with successful entrepreneurs. This provides students with role models, practical advice, and support, enhancing their entrepreneurial learning (St-Jean & Audet, 2012).

Increase Resources: Allocate more resources to EE programs, including funding for entrepreneurial projects, access to technology, and partnerships with industry. This investment can significantly improve the quality and reach of EE (Nabi et al., 2018).

Professional Development for Educators: Provide ongoing training for educators to enhance their entrepreneurial knowledge and teaching methods. Exposure to current entrepreneurial practices and continuous learning can equip educators to better mentor and inspire students (Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2006).

Policy Support: Develop and implement policies that support the integration and enhancement of EE in educational systems. Government and institutional support are crucial for sustaining and scaling up EE initiatives (European Commission, 2013).

By addressing these challenges and implementing the recommended improvements, EE programs can more effectively foster all dimensions of IEO, preparing students for successful entrepreneurial careers.

Pedagogical Approaches

Effective EE programs employ experiential learning, mentorship, and practical training to foster entrepreneurial behaviors (Neck & Greene, 2011, Anubhav et al., 2024). Experiential learning involves hands-on activities where

students actively engage in entrepreneurial tasks, which enhances their learning experience and retention of entrepreneurial concepts (Kolb, 1984). Such approaches include business simulations, real-world projects, internships, and participation in entrepreneurial competitions (Gibb, 1993; Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

Experiential Learning

Experiential learning is a cornerstone of effective EE, as it immerses students in real-world entrepreneurial environments (Kolb, 1984). This method allows students to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations, thereby enhancing their problem-solving skills and entrepreneurial thinking (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). For example, business simulations and entrepreneurial projects provide students with opportunities to develop business plans, manage virtual companies, and make strategic decisions in a controlled setting (Gibb, 1993). Such experiences are invaluable in preparing students for the challenges of actual entrepreneurial ventures (Rae & Carswell, 2001).

Mentorship

Mentorship is another critical component of effective EE programs (St-Jean & Audet, 2012; Patel et al., 2024). Experienced entrepreneurs provide guidance, support, and valuable insights to students, helping them navigate the complexities of starting and running a business (St-Jean & Audet, 2012). Mentors can offer practical advice, share their experiences, and serve as role models, which significantly enhances the learning experience (Bisk, 2002). The presence of mentors can also boost students' confidence and entrepreneurial self-efficacy, essential traits for successful entrepreneurship (St-Jean & Tremblay, 2011).

Practical Training

Practical training in EE programs involves direct engagement with entrepreneurial activities, such as creating and managing student-run businesses or participating in business incubation programs (Honig, 2004). This hands-on approach helps students gain practical skills, such as financial management, marketing, and operations, which are crucial for entrepreneurial success (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). Additionally, practical training provides an opportunity for students to learn from their failures and successes, fostering resilience and adaptability (Neck & Greene, 2011).

Challenges in Pedagogical Approaches

Despite the benefits of these pedagogical approaches, several challenges hinder their effective implementation (Nabi et al., 2018). One major challenge is limited mentorship availability. Many EE programs struggle to find enough experienced entrepreneurs willing to dedicate time to mentoring students (St-Jean & Audet, 2012). This shortage can significantly affect the quality of mentorship provided, limiting students' exposure to real-world entrepreneurial insights (Bisk, 2002).

Another challenge is the minimal experiential learning opportunities available to students (Honig, 2004). Limited access to business simulations, internships, and entrepreneurial projects can reduce the effectiveness of EE programs (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012). Without these opportunities, students may not fully develop the practical skills and entrepreneurial mindset needed for success (Kolb, 1984).

Inadequate teaching methods also pose a significant challenge (Neck & Greene, 2011). Traditional lecture-based teaching methods may not effectively engage students or foster the development of entrepreneurial skills (Gibb, 1993). Educators need to adopt more interactive and student-centered teaching approaches to enhance the effectiveness of EE (Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

Recommendations for Enhancing Pedagogical Approaches

To address these challenges and improve the effectiveness of EE, several recommendations can be made (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). Firstly, increasing the availability of mentorship opportunities is crucial. Establishing partnerships with local businesses and entrepreneurial networks can help secure more mentors for EE programs (St-Jean & Tremblay, 2011). Additionally, integrating technology-based mentoring platforms can connect students with mentors from diverse geographical locations, enhancing their learning experience (Bisk, 2002).

Secondly, expanding experiential learning opportunities is essential (Kolb, 1984). Educational institutions should invest in creating more business simulation programs, internships, and entrepreneurial projects (Gibb, 1993). Collaborating with industry partners to provide real-world projects and internships can significantly enrich students' learning experiences (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012).

Thirdly, improving teaching methods is vital (Neck & Greene, 2011). Educators should be trained in interactive and experiential teaching techniques to engage students more effectively (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). Incorporating case studies, group projects, and active learning strategies can enhance students' understanding and application of entrepreneurial concepts (Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

Pedagogical approaches play a crucial role in the effectiveness of EE programs. By employing experiential learning, mentorship, and practical training, educational institutions can significantly enhance the entrepreneurial orientation of students. However, addressing the challenges of limited mentorship, minimal experiential learning opportunities, and inadequate teaching methods is essential to maximize the impact of EE. Implementing the recommended strategies can help overcome these challenges and foster a more robust entrepreneurial ecosystem in educational settings.

DISCUSSION

EE has a positive influence on different aspects of IEO including innovation and proactiveness (Gibb, 1993; Kolb, 1984). This is observable in the way EE programs are designed to foster creative thinking and action-oriented behavior necessary for entrepreneurial success (Cope & Pittaway, 2007). Students participating in EE often become better at producing new ideas as well as predicting future business trends (Greene & Neck, 2011).

Nevertheless, the relatively weak effect on risk-taking and autonomy suggests that existing EE programs might require reconsideration. Risk-taking represents one of the most important dimensions of entrepreneurship, referring to the willingness to undertake businesses with uncertain outcomes (Shepherd & McMullen, 2006). There might be few situations within the current EE curricula where students are allowed to practice risk assessment and decision-making under uncertainty (Honig, 2004).

Similarly, another area that needs improvement is autonomy which is defined as independent action and decision making. Autonomy in entrepreneurship means self-direction and being able to take an initiative without external control. Hence, these programs need to promote self-sufficiency among individuals as well as self-employment skills (Carswell & Rae, 2001).

Making Mentorship stronger

One way of dealing with these issues is enhancing mentorship through EE programs (St-Jean & Audet, 2012). Mentors can give practical insights needed by students especially when it comes to navigating complex entrepreneurial landscapes. Effective mentorship involves regular interaction between mentors and mentees thus leading to feedback loops plus support systems aimed at improving student's entrepreneurial skills among them being risk taking and autonomy dimensions (Biski et al., 2002). For instance, educational institutions can create strong mentorship networks that will help students expand their learning by accessing the experience of successful entrepreneurs who have achieved much financial success from their ventures (Beugre et al., 2011).

Mentorship plays an integral role in improving entrepreneur's skills and self-efficacy. For budding entrepreneurs, this is important because mentors who are experienced entrepreneurs have valuable advice that helps new entrepreneurs (Biski et al., 2002). This way, such mentors would share their own experiences including failures to help mentees develop a realistic perspective of entrepreneurship (Audet & Jean, 2012). Additionally, mentorship can create an atmosphere of support where students can take calculated risks and make autonomous decisions which would enhance both risk-taking and autonomy dimensions (Beugre et al., 2011).

Adding Experiential Learning

Another way of advancing EE programs is through engaging

them more in experiential learning activities (Kolb, 1984). In so doing they got involved in performing actual entrepreneurial activities using theoretical knowledge (Cope & Pittaway, 2007; Mutambo et al. 2022). Instead, projects like simulations in business, internships or any other enterprise exercises can give these students the chance to try out on how they could manage different risks while making their own choices freely (Gibb, 1993). It does not only improve practical skills but also build confidence and resilience required for successful entrepreneurship (Carswell & Rae, 2001).

Experience based learning helps bridge the gap between theory and practice. Activities such as internships enable students to work with seasoned entrepreneurs giving them insights into the daily challenges as well as decision-making processes inherent in running a business venture (Greene & Neck, 2011). On the other hand, business simulations as well as entrepreneurial projects allow learners to try out diverse approaches within a safe environment for them to understand better business dynamics alongside risk management (Honig, 2004).

Innovative Ways of Teaching

For effective EE delivery it is necessary to adopt innovative teaching methods (Greene & Neck, 2011). By employing student-centered approaches such as case studies, group work, and active learning strategies, EE can be made more interesting and effective (Gailly & Fayolle, 2008). This encourages student to think deeply, cooperate with others and utilize their knowledge in such a manner that it can be applied in real life activities which makes them better entrepreneurs (Edwards & Pittaway, 2012).

One of the goals of innovative teaching should be to make learning immersive. In this regard, case studies provide real-life situations that enable students to come up with strategies for business and make decisions, hence enhancing their thinking critically (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). Additionally, these projects teach learners how to work within teams while still fostering the skills necessary for entrepreneurs who are successful leaders (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012). Other active learning methods like role playing and peer reviews can also be used in order for students to engage deeper into entrepreneurship concepts (Neck & Greene, 2011).

Policy and Resource Support

Good policy support is required for effective environmental education as well.

For example, governments and educational institutions must prioritize EE by providing funding, infrastructure and a conducive policy environment (Nabi et al., 2018; Mutambo et al. 2022). The reason behind this is that they need to invest in technology among others so as there could be comprehensive EE curricula as well as having partnership with private sectors that offers real world experiences (World Bank, 2018).

The growth and success of EE programs requires sufficient policy support. This entails developing policies that

encourage entrepreneurial activities while supporting educational initiatives (European Commission, 2013). Among other things involved here include giving grants or financial incentives to schools that will develop and implement EE program or establishing partnerships between academic institutions and industrial partners (Nabi et al., 2018). In addition, good resources such as high-quality technology tools and modernized teaching facilities play a critical role in ensuring that efficient delivery of training takes place in various centers offering EE services (World Bank, 2018).

Cultural and Contextual Factors

It is also important to study cultural contexts since they dictate the importance of entrepreneurship education. For instance, cultural attitudes towards enterprise may differ significantly between different regions thereby influencing reception of EE programs implemented there in (Dana, 1995). For example, some cultures stigmatize entrepreneurial failure, a thing that can discourage risk taking and innovation. Consequently, EE programs need to be adjusted towards these cultural subtleties to encourage more supportive entrepreneurship platforms (Thomas & Mueller, 2000).

Moreover, the economic and regulatory environment can affect the success of EE initiatives. For instance, some regions with developed entrepreneurship ecosystems such as financing options and regulatory support are favorable to the adoption of EE programs (Isenberg, 2011). Conversely, if there is a restrictive legal environment or lack of access to resources then it may be difficult for EE programs to succeed. Thus, adjustment of these programmes basing on localities is highly necessary to achieve their maximum potential (Isenberg, 2011).

Long-Term Impact and Sustainability

Another important area of concern is how effective has EE been in shaping students' entrepreneurial careers in his/her future life? Longitudinal studies provide useful information on how EE affects entrepreneurial intentions over time as well as how successful entrepreneurs are made by this program (Peterman & Kennedy, 2003). Furthermore, monitoring the entrepreneurial outcomes of graduates from various institutions offering EE will assist in determining the long-term benefits accrued from this form of teaching and help identify areas that needs improvement (Peterman & Kennedy, 2003).

Sustainability of EE programs is also a key consideration. For this reason, appropriate funding mechanisms should always be put in place alongside institutional backing so that such programs can run smoothly for many years. Strategic planning can lead to securing multiple sources of income while partnerships with stakeholders' help build strong collaborations thus safeguarding sustainability (Hannon, 2005). This approach ensures that educational institutions can grow EEs which will remain relevant for generations yet unborn (Hannon, 2005).

Gender and inclusivity in EE

Another important consideration is gender and inclusivity in EE which research has shown often that women and marginalized groups are likely to face unique challenges while venturing into entrepreneurship such as access to capital support and network (Brush, 1992). These EE programs should be inclusive, having specialized assistance and backing for underrepresented groups guaranteeing equal opportunities for all aspiring entrepreneurs (Brush et al., 2009).

For instance, these exclusive EE programs can offer mentorship, networking opportunities or financial aid specifically targeting women and other marginalized groups (Brush et al., 2009). In this way, not only does promoting diversity in entrepreneurship enhances social justice but also enriches the general entrepreneurial system by allowing variety of views and notions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Curriculum Development

Include More Realistic and Experiential Education Elements in the EE Coursework.

According to Kolb (1984), practical learning is essential for bridging the gap between knowledge that is theoretical and its real application. Business simulations, internships, and entrepreneurial projects are examples of practical and experiential learning elements that should be integrated into the EE curricula (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). This allows students to gain first-hand experience in entrepreneurship thus promoting their entrepreneurial skills while at the same time equipping them with problem-solving, risk management or decision-making skills.

1. Improve Mentorship Programs for Students to Gain Actual Entrepreneurial Experience.

Effective EE programs must include mentorship as part of it (St-Jean & Audet, 2012). Building strong mentorship opportunities for students through which they can connect with experienced entrepreneurs can be very helpful as a source of practical advice about starting and running a business. In addition to providing guidance during start-up processes, these mentors may share their own entrepreneurial journeys while helping pupils navigate difficulties associated with establishing and managing enterprises. When these practices are undertaken students become better problem solvers, good risk managers as well as improved decision makers.

2. Training for Educators

Improve Teachers' Methods of Instruction and Understanding about Enterprise through Professional Development Programs

One key player in effective delivery of EE programs is an educator. Continuous professional development should be provided to educators thereby improving their teaching methods within entrepreneurship (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008).

The training programs should concentrate on interactive teaching techniques that involve practice to make teachers more engaging. Furthermore, educators ought to keep themselves updated with current entrepreneurial practices hence making sure their knowledge is relevant (Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2006; (Mutambo et al. 2022).

3. Policy Support

Strengthening Policy Frameworks towards Ensuring Integration of Entrepreneurship Education in TEVET Institutions

The success of EE programs largely depends on government policies (European Commission, 2013). It is therefore essential to strengthen policy frameworks that support the integration of EE in TEVET institutions. Policies must promote the teaching of entrepreneurship at all levels of education with it being a core component in the curriculum. Additionally, policies may have to create alliances between schools and private sector, thus enabling students access many mentors (Nabi et al., 2018).

Provide Funding and Resources for Improving EE Delivery

To improve delivery of EE programs sufficient funding and resources are required (World Bank, 2018). Government and learning institutions need to allocate substantial financial resources towards quality development and maintenance of EE programs. This should include investment in technology as well as learning materials while supporting experiential learning through infrastructure. In addition, funds set aside can be used to train teachers and establish mentorship programmes which becomes an all-round support system for entrepreneurship education (Nabi et al., 2018) to promote effectiveness and efficiency (Mutambo et al. 2022).

Research and Evaluation

Conduct Longitudinal Studies to Assess the Long-Term Impact of EE on IEO:

To know the long-term effects of EE on Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO), it is necessary for one to undertake longitudinal studies in this area (Peterman & Kennedy, 2003). These studies help in tracking entrepreneurial results of EE graduates over time which are important for understanding how much has been put into entrepreneurship (Neck & Greene, 2011). Such research can only be achieved by conducting a longitudinal study that looks for strengths and weaknesses of current entrepreneurship education course offerings that could be used in guiding future changes for its improvement.

Evaluate the Effectiveness of Different Pedagogical Approaches in Fostering Entrepreneurial Orientation:

Evaluating the effectiveness of various pedagogical approaches towards entrepreneurial orientation is essential since it ensures continuous improvement (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). The analysis should establish whether there exists any effect from engagement via learning by doing (experiential

teaching), apprenticing (mentorship) or interactive methods such as exercises or causerie among students’ development of entrepreneurial interests. Educators need to identify most effective ways to break down barriers that prevent the attainment of benefits gained from practical learning within educational programs designed for entrepreneurs-to-be.

Finally, adopting these suggestions will significantly improve EE activities as they will go a long way in training students with notable entrepreneurial mindsets. Inclusion of practical and experiential components in curriculum as well as strengthening mentorship programs; offering professional development for educators; improving policy frameworks; undertaking comprehensive research and evaluation are some of these measures. These efforts will contribute to developing vibrant ecosystems for fostering entrepreneurship leading ultimately to economic growth and innovation.

CONCLUSION

This reviews article synthesizes existing literature on the impact of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) on Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) within Technical Education Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training (TEVET) institutions in Zambia. The results of the study show that EE has a significant positive influence on various aspects of individualized entrepreneurial orientation (IEO) such as innovation, competitive aggressiveness, achievement orientation, learning orientation, passion and proactiveness (Neck & Greene, 2011). These dimensions of IEO are vital in making these students realize that they are likely to succeed in businesses.

The review also identifies areas where EE programs need improvement, particularly in enhancing students’ risk-taking and autonomy. In this context, it is important for an entrepreneur to be ready to seize any opportunity especially if its outcome cannot be predicted with certainty; and have the capability to make decisions independently. Such characteristics may not be addressed by the existing program due to lack of real-life contexts.

These challenges can only be tackled from various angles. Mentorship should be improved within EE programs because mentors provide practical insights, guidance and support which can go a long way in improving students’ entrepreneurial skills. Establishing strong mentorship networks with experienced entrepreneurs can enrich students’ learning experiences and boost their confidence in taking calculated risks and making independent decisions.

Another indispensable strategy is having more experiential learning opportunities as part of EE curricula. Experiential learning strategies help connect abstract knowledge with actual implementation thereby enabling learners take part in authentic entrepreneurial tasks. Some actual illustrations include business simulations, internships or even entrepreneurship projects among others whereby students acquire hands-on experience on how to manage risks as well

as make autonomous decisions that would improve their practical skills besides resilience.

Further development of entrepreneurship education should focus on innovative teaching methods. Interactive teaching methods that encourage active participation like case studies, group projects or active learning programs can improve the quality of entrepreneurial education offered by many schools (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). In this respect interactive approaches emphasize critical thinking through student involvement so they could use their knowledge effectively under changeable conditions that is necessary to have a deeper understanding of entrepreneurship.

For EE programs to develop and be effective over time there is a need for policy support and adequate resources. In order that governments and education institutions assign funds, infrastructure and a conducive policy environment in favor of EE, countries must ensure that they prioritize it. It encompasses investing in technology, coming up with holistic EE curricula as well as forging partnerships with the private sectors to offer real-life learning experiences.

The cultural and contextual factors that influence the effectiveness of EE should also be considered when implementing them. There are many nuances in culture that need to be addressed if one is to create an entrepreneurial friendly environment through which such programs can be more useful. This may include studying the long-term effects of EE on students' entrepreneurial careers through longitudinal studies to determine what can work eventually. By implementing these recommendations, policymakers and educators can significantly enhance the effectiveness of EE programs in fostering a strong entrepreneurial orientation among vocational students. These efforts will contribute to the development of a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem in Zambia, ultimately driving economic growth and innovation.

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